

Agroforestry contributes to circular bioeconomy

www.eurafagroforestry.eu/afinet/

Economic growth has usually been at the expense of the environment. The need to change our development to a more sustainable economic model, makes circular bioeconomy to be part of the solution to address some of the most eminent European and global challenges. Given that most products derived from fossil fuels can be obtained from biomass, either woody or other plant species, the opportunities for agroforestry are manifold. Agroforestry is known for the diversification of products that can be obtained in an integrative way in the same land unit, providing a great variety of raw materials from trees, crops or livestock that may be transformed into bio-based products. Trees provide timber but also wood-based textile fibers. Pruning and fellings in forests provide biomass that can be used as pellets, biochar, mulching... Birch sap is used for drinks and sweeteners, juices can also be obtained from spruce needles... Crops can be used for carbon fibers, cellulose, acids with a wide range of uses... Agricultural waste can be converted in bioplastics. Textiles can be obtained from powdered milk, bone meal can serve as fertilizer, dairy whey can be converted in a green solvent... These are only a few of the examples of bioproducts that could be obtained in agroforestry systems.

References:

AFINET factsheet:

https://euraf.isa.utl.pt/files/pub/20190513_factsheet_07_-_web.pdf#overlay-context=afinet/materials/factsheet

Platform about bio-based products: www.allthings.bio

Bioplastics made from rice. Adobe Stock.

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